

**The Impact of AI Tools on Programming Learning Efficiency among Astana
IT University Students**

Galidullayeva A., Ushkempir D., Marat Y., Bolatkhanuly A.
Astana IT University

Academic Writing
Yevgeniya Verba

May 24, 2026

Abstract

This study examines the impact of AI tools on learning effectiveness specifically within the programming environment for students at Astana IT University. The main issue is that tools such as ChatGPT, Copilot, Gemini and Cursor Cloud can help students complete tasks more quickly, but it is not always clear whether this actually improves their understanding of coding. The main aim of the study is to determine how the use of such AI tools affects the balance between the rapid completion of a specific task and an understanding of the overall concept. A mixed-methods approach was used in the study: an online survey using Google Forms and interviews with students at Astana IT University. The results showed that AI significantly improves performance in terms of task completion speed, as well as identifying errors during coding and reducing stress; however, excessive use of AI leads to a reduction in independence when solving problems. Therefore, AI should be used primarily as a supporting tool, but not as a substitute for human thinking.

Research Context (Introduction)

AI tools are becoming common in higher education institutions that teach programming. Students currently use tools like ChatGPT, Copilot, Gemini and Cursor Cloud when writing code, fixing bugs, completing assignments, learning programming concepts or seeking fast explanations. This change is important, because programming is a complex subject that requires logical thinking, problem-solving, syntax knowledge, and regular practice.

Previous studies show that AI tools can have a positive influence on programming-related learning. Chang (2025) found that generative AI tools can improve learning effectiveness, motivation, and cooperation in programming-related courses. Similarly, Yilmaz and Yilmaz (2023) reported that students who used ChatGPT in programming education showed higher computational thinking skills, programming self-efficacy, and motivation. Fan et al. (2025) also found that AI-assisted pair programming increased students' intrinsic motivation, reduced programming anxiety, and improved programming performance. In addition, Alanazi et al. (2025) showed that AI tools can improve programming performance and reduce task completion time.

However, the use of AI tools in programming education also creates considerable difficulties. Completing a task faster does not always mean fully understanding it. Alanazi et al. (2025) emphasized that despite AI tools improve performance or efficiency, their impact on deep understanding may be limited. This suggests that students may complete assignments faster without fully understanding the logic behind of the code. Hence, overreliance on AI may reduce independent problem-solving skills as well as critical thinking.

This issue is especially relevant for Astana IT University students because many of them study programming and use AI tools during their academic courses. However, other existing studies have been conducted in other educational contexts and at universities in other countries, such as universities in Taiwan, Turkey, China, or broader international settings. Therefore, their findings may not fully reflect the experience of AITU students, their curriculum, and their learning habits.

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of generative AI tools on the effectiveness of learning programming to undergraduate students of Astana IT University. This research is significant because it examines the finding a balance between task completion speed and actual conceptual understanding. Main research question: To what extent does the use of AI tools affect programming learning efficiency among AITU students?

In addition, the research may provide useful insights for educators at Astana IT University about the impact of AI-assisted learning on students' academic performance and conceptual understanding. The study may also contribute to future research related to AI integration in higher education and programming learning environments.

Extended Definition

AI-assisted programming learning involves the use of AI tools such as ChatGPT, Copilot, Gemini and other similar systems to provide comprehensive support to students in the field of programming. Providing quick hints, explaining code and assisting with debugging are the primary tasks of AI tools in coding. Chang (2025) writes that AI tools can improve learning and motivation in terms of effectiveness. However, AI should not replace the student's own thinking. Alanazi et al. (2025) emphasize that the use of artificial intelligence improves performance and the efficiency of task completion, but its impact on full understanding is severely limited. Therefore, in the study, AI-assisted programming learning refers to the use of AI as an aid to achieve faster and more effective results, whilst the student retains their own critical thinking and problem-solving approach.

Methods

This study adopted a mixed-methods approach, integrating both online surveys and qualitative interviews. This approach was chosen because the goal of the study was not only to identify general trends in students' use of AI tools but also to gain a deeper understanding of their personal experiences learning programming.

The quantitative part of the study was conducted as an online survey via Google Forms. The survey aimed to determine which AI tools students use most frequently, for

what purposes they use them, and how they perceive the impact of AI on learning programming. Questions focused on the use of ChatGPT, Copilot, Gemini and Cursor Cloud or other tools for understanding programming concepts, completing assignments, finding errors, analyzing lectures, and reducing stress. This format allowed us to collect numerical data and identify key trends among participants while maintaining the confidentiality of each participant.

Forty-seven students studying programming at Astana IT University participated in the survey. The study focuses specifically on the impact of AI tools on programming learning efficiency among students who actually encounter coding tasks, debugging, and programming assignments.

The qualitative part of the study was conducted through an individual semi-structured interview with one participant. The interview aimed to gain a deeper understanding of how the student uses AI in the learning process. The main topics of the interviews were: using AI to explain code, speeding up assignments, and potential reliance on AI. This format was chosen because individual interviews allow for more detailed responses and examples of personal experiences without any restrictions.

Before data collection, participants were informed of the purpose of the study and signed consent form. Participants took part of their own free will, and responses were used for educational purposes only. Participants' personal information was not disclosed.

The survey data was evaluated using percentages and overall trends. The results were shown through quantitative metrics, such as the frequency of AI tool use and the primary purposes for which they were used.

Results

The results showed that artificial intelligence tools are actively used by students at Astana IT University when studying programming and coding. 47 AITU students studying programming took part in the survey. The quantitative data showed that ChatGPT is one of the most popular tools. 67.4% of participants indicated that it is their primary artificial intelligence tool. Furthermore, 54.3% stated that it is used to complete assignments, 58.7% said it is used to understand programming concepts, and 54.3% noted that artificial intelligence is very effective at reducing stress whilst programming. And 69.6% believe that artificial intelligence has a positive impact on learning, self-study or as a tutor.

This trend shows us that students use artificial intelligence in a variety of ways, not only for writing code, explaining complex topics, finding debugging solutions, analyzing lectures to prepare for exams and quizzes. This means that students perceive artificial intelligence more as a learning aid rather than merely a tool.

Qualitative data was obtained through interviews with students at Astana IT University; this approach helped to gain a deeper understanding of the specific ways and

methods in which students use AI in the learning process, and the advantages and disadvantages they associate with its use.

Discussion

This research and its findings demonstrate that artificial intelligence tools have a positive impact on the effectiveness of programming education among students at Astana IT University. Data from a Google survey indicates that students most frequently use these tools to gain a deeper understanding of coding and to complete tasks in this field. This answers the research question, as it demonstrates that artificial intelligence not only help students complete tasks more quickly but also support their understanding the material better. Individual interviews also showed us that artificial intelligence can hinder independent problem-solving. This trend is also evident in the survey responses.

The results align with the findings of Chang (2025), who noted that generative tools improve efficiency and collaboration in programming-related courses. They also support the research by Yilmaz and Yilmaz (2023), where ChatGPT was used to enhance computational thinking, programming efficiency and motivation. Fan et al. (2025) demonstrated that an AI assistant reduces stress and improves performance, and our results confirm the cautiously positive stance of Alanazi et al. (2025), namely that these tools improve performance and task completion efficiency, but their impact is limited in terms of deep understanding.

The study has limitations. Firstly, the sample consisted of AITU students, specifically 47 students, so these results cannot be considered fully representative of all universities in Kazakhstan. Secondly, the qualitative part is based solely on individual interviews. Thirdly, the survey reflects only the students' self-assessment, rather than an actual assessment of their coding skills. Future studies should utilise a larger sample, conduct more interviews, and include a practical programming test before and after the use of artificial intelligence.

References

- Alanazi, M., Soh, B., Samra, H., & Li, A. (2025). The influence of artificial intelligence tools on learning outcomes in computer programming: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Computers, 14*(5), 185. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers14050185>
- Chang, C.-C. (2025). Evaluating the impact of generative AI tools on learning outcomes, motivation, and cooperation in programming-related courses. *International Journal of Education and Research, 13*(2), 55–66.
- Fan, G., Liu, D., Zhang, R., & Pan, L. (2025). The impact of AI-assisted pair programming on student motivation, programming anxiety, collaborative learning, and programming performance: A comparative study with traditional pair programming and individual approaches. *International Journal of STEM Education, 12*, Article 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-025-00537-3>
- Yilmaz, R., & Yilmaz, F. G. K. (2023). The effect of generative artificial intelligence (AI)-based tool use on students' computational thinking skills, programming self-efficacy and motivation. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence, 4*, 100147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2023.100147>